

ADAPTIVE STREAMLINE TRACING FOR STREAMLINE SIMULATION ON IRREGULAR GRIDS

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ABSTRACT

Streamline simulation relies on an efficient and accurate calculation of streamlines and time-of-flight coordinates (TOF). Computation of streamlines are commonly done on a cell-by-cell basis using flux interpolation in the semi-analytical Pollock's method. An alternative method is to use corner-point velocity interpolation in each grid-cell, which reproduces uniform flow in three spatial dimensions. For this method, numerical integration of streamlines is required. In previous work, streamlines for irregular hexahedrons have been obtained by numerical integration in a reference cube, which facilitates easy detection of cell boundaries. The disadvantage of this method is the computational cost of transforming the velocity from physical space to a reference element, involving multiple evaluations of the Jacobian matrix. In this work, we propose an adaptive method for integration of streamlines directly in physical space, which aims at higher computational efficiency by reducing the number of evaluations of the Jacobian matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

For a given velocity field $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x})$, a family of streamlines $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s}(\tau; \mathbf{x}_0)$ is defined by

$$\frac{d\mathbf{s}}{d\tau} = \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{s}(0; \mathbf{x}_0) = \mathbf{x}_0, \quad (1)$$

where τ parameterizes the streamline passing through the starting point \mathbf{x}_0 .

We consider streamline tracing in the context of streamline simulation of (multiphase) flow in hydrocarbon reservoirs [Batycky, 1997; Bratvedt et al., 1993; King and Datta-Gupta, 1998]. Multiphase flow in porous media can be modelled by a set of partial differential equations. Using the so-called fractional flow formulation, the flow of e.g., two phases can be described by a parabolic equation for the fluid pressure and a (hyperbolic) transport equation for fluid saturations. The basis for any streamline method is a sequential splitting of the coupled system of pressure and saturation equations, in which one first fixes the saturation and solves the pressure equation. The velocity field, which is linked to the pressure through Darcy's law, is then used as a parameter while advancing the transport equation a given step forward in time. The new saturation field is then used as input parameter for a new pressure solution step, and so on.

Introducing the time-of-flight coordinate [Batycky, 1997] as an integral along a streamline,

$$\tau(x, y, z) = \int_{s_0}^s \frac{\phi}{|\mathbf{q}|} ds, \quad (2)$$

the multidimensional saturation equation can be transformed into a family of one-dimensional equations along streamlines, which can be used to speed up the numerical solution of fluid transport. In this work we will consider how to compute streamlines and time-of-flight from the solution of the pressure equation. The pressure equation will be solved by a mass-conservative scheme, e.g. an MPFA (O-method) [Aavatsmark, 2002], providing continuous fluxes on grid cell edges. We consider applications on 2D quadrilateral grids, where a continuously defined velocity field is commonly obtained by interpolation of the quadrilateral edge-fluxes [Jimenez et al., 2005; Prévost et al., 2002]. The extension of the proposed method to 3D is indicated.

2. STREAMLINE TRACING ON IRREGULAR GRIDS

2.1. Introduction: Tracing on Cartesian Grids. We start with a discussion of streamline tracing on 2D Cartesian grids, commonly referred to as Pollock's method [Pollock, 1988] in the literature. Pollock's method builds a streamline as a series of line segments that each crosses a grid cell in physical space. The segments are constructed such that the exit point of the streamline in one cell is the entrance point in the next cell. By introducing a coordinate transformation, each rectangular grid cell is transformed into a unit square. Linear interpolation of (scaled) edge fluxes is then used to define a velocity field:

$$\mathbf{q}^I(x, y) \equiv \begin{bmatrix} F_{x0}(1-x) + F_{x1}x \\ F_{y0}(1-y) + F_{y1}y \end{bmatrix}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1. \quad (3)$$

Having defined a velocity field, the streamline $\mathbf{s}(\tau) = [x(\tau), y(\tau)]$ (on the unit square) is found by integrating the system of ODEs in (1):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = q_x^I(x), & x(0) = x_0, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = q_y^I(y), & y(0) = y_0, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where q_x^I and q_y^I are the x - and y -components of \mathbf{q}^I . Since q_x^I depends only on x , and q_y^I depends only on y , the streamline can be found analytically [Pollock, 1988]. Finally, the streamline is mapped back to the original grid cell.

2.2. Streamline and Velocity in Curvilinear Coordinates. Irregular grids are commonly used in reservoir description, due to ease of discretization and improved mesh quality. We consider irregular quadrilaterals in 2D, which are images of a unit square under the bilinear transformation,

$$\mathbf{x}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^4 \mathbf{x}_i \phi_i(\hat{x}, \hat{y}), \quad 0 \leq \hat{x}, \hat{y} \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i = [x_i, y_i]$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$, are the four corner points of the quadrilateral, $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = [\hat{x}, \hat{y}]$ is a point in the unit square (the reference space \mathcal{R}); $\mathbf{x}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = [x(\hat{x}, \hat{y}), y(\hat{x}, \hat{y})]$ is a point in the

FIGURE 1. Left: Transformation of a streamline and velocity from reference space \mathcal{R} to physical space \mathcal{P} . Right: Reconstructing velocities from fluxes

quadrilateral (physical space \mathcal{P}); and $\phi_i(\hat{x}, \hat{y})$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$, are the standard bilinear shape functions on the unit square. Note that the extension of the method to 3D will consider hexahedral grid cells that are images of a unit cube under a trilinear transformation.

Velocity Transformation. Commonly, streamlines are integrated (traced) in \mathcal{R} and then mapped back to \mathcal{P} . To integrate a streamline $\hat{\mathbf{s}}(t)$ in \mathcal{R} , the velocity must be given in bilinear coordinates. An expression for this velocity may be derived as follows: To obtain the streamline $\mathbf{s}(t)$ in \mathcal{P} , the bilinear transformation is applied to the streamline $\hat{\mathbf{s}}(t)$ in \mathcal{R} ; see Figure 1 (left). We then use the chain rule to determine the velocity in \mathcal{R} ,

$$\mathbf{q} \equiv \frac{d\mathbf{s}}{dt} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}(t))}{dt} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\hat{\mathbf{x}}} \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{s}}}{dt} = \mathbf{J}\hat{\mathbf{q}}. \quad (6)$$

Here $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = d\hat{\mathbf{s}}/dt$ is the velocity in \mathcal{R} , \mathbf{q} is the velocity in \mathcal{P} , and $\mathbf{J} = d\mathbf{x}/d\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is the Jacobian matrix of the transformation. Thus, the transformed velocity is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{q}. \quad (7)$$

3. CORNER VELOCITY INTERPOLATION

The standard methods [Cordes and Kinzelbach, 1992; Jimenez et al., 2005; Prévost et al., 2002] for streamline tracing on irregular grids are based on integration in \mathcal{R} , approximating $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ in Eq. (7) using a linear interpolation of the edge fluxes. In [Hægland et al., 2005] it was shown that these methods may fail to reproduce uniform flow on irregular grids in 3D. To remedy this situation, a velocity interpolation scheme denoted *corner velocity interpolation* (CVI) was introduced. A central idea of this method is the shift from flux interpolation to corner-point velocity interpolation.

Reconstruction of Corner Velocities. The method is described here for the 2D case, see [Hægland et al., 2005] for details of the 3D case. Consider the cell shown in Figure 1 (right), where four fluxes F_i , are given on the edges E_i , $i = x0, x1, y0, y1$. Normal vectors \mathbf{n}_i with direction consistent with the sign of the edge fluxes are defined for each edge E_i . The length (absolute value) of the normal vectors are assumed to be equal to the length of the corresponding edge. Corner velocities \mathbf{q}_i , $i = 1, \dots, 4$, at the corners \mathbf{x}_i , can then be obtained by solving 2×2 linear systems on the form

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{q}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{x(i)} = F_{x(i)}, \\ \mathbf{q}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{y(i)} = F_{y(i)}, \end{cases} \quad i = 1, \dots, 4, \quad (8)$$

where $\{x(i)\}_{i=1}^4 = \{x0, x1, x1, x0\}$ and $\{y(i)\}_{i=1}^4 = \{y0, y0, y1, y1\}$, refer to edges in the x - and y -direction, respectively, adjacent to corner \mathbf{x}_i . This means that to determine \mathbf{q}_1 , we solve

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{q}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{x0} = F_{x0}, \\ \mathbf{q}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{y0} = F_{y0}, \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

since E_{x0} and E_{y0} are adjacent to corner \mathbf{x}_1 . The systems (8) are well-conditioned as long as the quadrilateral does not degenerate. If the fluxes have been computed exactly for a uniform flow field \mathbf{q} , then $\mathbf{q}_i = \mathbf{q}$. See *Hægland et al.* [2005] for more details.

The CVIR Method. The method of *corner velocity interpolation in reference space* (CVIR) is based on integration of (7) in \mathcal{R} , where the unknown quantity is the velocity \mathbf{q} in \mathcal{P} . We approximate \mathbf{q} by a bilinear interpolation of the corner velocities \mathbf{q}_i in Equation (8),

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{CVIP}}^{\text{I}}(\mathbf{x}(\hat{x}, \hat{y})) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^4 \mathbf{q}_i \phi_i(\hat{x}, \hat{y}), \quad (10)$$

where ϕ_i and \mathbf{x} have the same meaning as in Eq. (5). Note that (10) is exact for uniform flow. The method of *corner velocity interpolation in physical space* (CVIP) to be described in the next section, integrates the velocity in (10) directly in physical space, hence the subscript CVIP in (10). The difficulty with this approach is to determine when cell boundaries are crossed, especially in 3D. Thus, integration on a reference element was suggested in *Hægland et al.* [2005], leading to the CVIR method characterized by the following velocity interpolation in \mathcal{R} ,

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{\text{CVIR}}^{\text{I}} \equiv \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{q}_{\text{CVIP}}^{\text{I}}, \quad (11)$$

where we have used (7). The disadvantage of the CVIR-method is the expensive evaluation of the inverse Jacobian matrix at each integration point.

4. TRACING IN PHYSICAL SPACE. THE CVIP METHOD

In [*Hægland et al.*, 2005], a forth-order Runge-Kutta method (RK45) was used for integration with the CVIR method, which requires six function evaluations (i.e. evaluations of velocity) per time step. For each velocity evaluation we need to determine the inverse of the Jacobian, see (11). In order to avoid this expensive step, we would like to consider integration in the physical space. Integration in \mathcal{P} involves the difficulty of determining the exit point from a cell, additionally, if we use a Runge-Kutta method, function evaluations (velocity) at intermediate points in physical coordinates are needed, whereas the velocity at these points is given in reference coordinates, see (10). This means that an inverse bilinear transformation must be used to determine the velocity at these points, which is even more expensive than evaluating the inverse Jacobian matrix.

In this paper we instead apply an Euler predictor-corrector method for integration in \mathcal{P} , which only requires the velocity at points on the cell boundaries. At such points, the inverse bilinear transformation will simplify to a linear relation, and the velocity in (10) can be easily evaluated. Adaptivity is implemented using a recursive mesh refinement procedure. Similar ideas have been explored in [*Bensabat et al.*, 2000; *Cheng et al.*, 1996]. Consider the quadrilateral grid cell shown in Figure 2 with reconstructed corner velocities \mathbf{q}_i at the corners \mathbf{x}_i , $i = 1, \dots, 4$, respectively. Within the cell, the velocity \mathbf{q} is given

FIGURE 2. Criterion for grid refinement

by the bilinear interpolation in (10). A particle enters the cell at \mathbf{p}_0 with velocity \mathbf{v}_0 (determined by the interpolation). If the flow field is uniform, the streamline through the cell will be a straight line, as indicated in the figure. An approach to check the validity of the assumption of uniform velocity is to compare the velocity \mathbf{v}_e at the exit point \mathbf{p}_e with \mathbf{v}_0 . Accordingly, we define the relative velocity error as

$$E_v = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_0 - \mathbf{v}_e\|}{\|\mathbf{v}_0\|} \quad (12)$$

If E_v is less than some prescribed tolerance ϵ , we accept the constant approximation $\mathbf{q} \approx \mathbf{v}_0$ (Euler method), or we rather use the improved estimate $\mathbf{q} \approx (1/2)(\mathbf{v}_0 + \mathbf{v}_e)$ (Euler predictor-corrector). If E_v is not less than ϵ , i.e., $\epsilon < E_v < E_{\max}$, where E_{\max} is a prescribed maximum error, an adaptive refinement of the grid cell will be employed. If E_v is greater than E_{\max} , we expect a high degree of refinement, and it would probably be more efficient to apply the RK45 method in reference space.

Mesh Refinement. The mesh refinement is based on a recursive splitting of a cell into four sub-cells. The splitting is defined by the coordinates of the bilinear transformation for a splitting of the the unit square in \mathcal{R} into four sub-squares of equal size, see Figure 2(b). If E_v exceeds ϵ for a given sub-cell, that sub-cell is recursively split into four new sub-cells. Note that the remaining three sub-cells may be left unrefined by this procedure.

5. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

To illustrate the method we consider numerical experiments in 2D. The extension to 3D is work in progress.

5.1. A Synthetic Case. Consider the test case in Figure 3. The domain has unit permeability, except in the cross-hatched area, where $K = 10^{-3}$. The boundary conditions are of Neumann type, with no-flow on top and bottom, inflow at edge AC, and outflow at edge BD. A single-phase pressure equation is solved using an MPFA-method on an irregular grid with 10×10 cells to provide continuous fluxes on each grid cell edge. The irregular grid is obtained from a Cartesian uniform grid, where each cell is a square with

FIGURE 3. Domain used in the first numerical test case. Streamlines for a Cartesian grid of the domain are shown to the right.

FIGURE 4. Streamlines for the first test case. Left: $\epsilon = 0.05$. Right: $\epsilon = 0.5$.

side length s_u . In order to keep the physical properties of the domain the same for different grid perturbations, only grid points in the interior of the left and right parts of the grid are perturbed. These points are perturbed within squares with side length s_p centered at the original grid point. For a $p\%$ perturbation we have $100s_p/s_u = p$, see Figure 4, where we have used a 50% perturbation.

Test 1: 10 Streamlines. Corner velocities for each grid cell are obtained from the fluxes using the recovery method from Section 3. For each integration method (CVIP/CVIR), ten streamlines are traced from ten fix points on the inflow boundary until they exit the domain at edge BD, see Figure 4. For the CVIR method, a fourth-order Runge-Kutta method with relative tolerance of 10^{-8} is used for integration in \mathcal{R} . Thus the streamlines traced with the CVIR method can be viewed as reference solutions for the given interpolated velocity field. Streamlines for CVIR and for CVIP with $\epsilon = 0.05$ and $\epsilon = 0.5$ are shown in Figure 4. The circles indicate the length of each local step in the CVIP method. We see the benefit of using the CVIP method for uniform flow (the middle of the domain in Figure 4), where no grid refinement is needed and the method is also exact. The influence of the streamline launching point on errors in streamline shape and time-of-flight has been investigated by *Matringe and Gerritsen* [2004]. They found that

streamlines should be started as far away from singularities (wells/fractures) as possible. In our test case we have a region with high streamline density (the fracture in the middle of the figure) and two regions with low streamline density (the inflow boundary and the outflow boundary). If we start the streamlines at the inflow boundary they will converge into the fracture, which will reduce errors. On the other hand, as the streamlines exit the fracture, they will diverge to the outflow boundary and the errors will increase, see Figure 4 (right). Still, it would be worse to launch the streamlines in the fracture and trace forward and backwards: For this case we then get the same errors at outflow boundary, but in addition we get errors at inflow boundary of the same size as for the outflow boundary.

Test 2: 100 Streamlines. We consider a sequence of relative tolerances $\{\epsilon_{i=1}^8\} = \{0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08, 0.16, 0.32, 0.64\}$. We increase the number of streamlines to 100, still starting at equally spaced points at the inflow boundary, and measure the error in the CVIP method at the right boundary BD compared to the reference solution given by the CVIR method. Two different error measures are applied: error in the exit position and error in time-of-flight at the exit point. We consider a sequence of grids with perturbations $\{p_{i=1}^6\} = \{0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50\}$. For each p_i and each ϵ_i , we take the average of the errors over the 100 streamlines. The resulting position errors are shown in Figure 5 (left). The

FIGURE 5. Left: Error in position. Right: Runtime for CVIP for different values of ϵ .

results for the time-of-flight error look similar. As expected, the errors are not sensitive to grid perturbation and increase with increased relative tolerance. Finally, we compare the runtime required for the CVIP and CVIR methods to trace all 100 streamlines for a given ϵ . We measure the runtime relative to the standard flux mapping (SFM) described in [Prévost et al., 2002]. This is a semi-analytical method for streamline tracing, and is commonly used in the industry due to its speed. Note that the extended flux mapping (EFM) by Jimenez et al. [2005], which is able to reproduce time-of-flight for uniform flow in 2D, is about as fast as the SFM method. The runtime for the CVIR and CVIP will be given in fractions of the runtime of the SFM method. For a MATLAB implementation, results for base-ten logarithm of the fraction for different tolerances ϵ_i , are shown in Figure 5 (right). A value of zero corresponds to the same runtime as the SFM. The

runtime of the CVIR method is approximately 15 times as long as the runtime of the SFM method. We see that the runtime of the CVIP method decreases as ϵ increases. The CVIP method is faster than the CVIR method for $\epsilon > 0.04$. For this specific case, there is a large reduction in runtime when going from $\epsilon = 0.04$ to approximately $\epsilon = 0.32$, where the CVIP method is about 12 times as fast as the CVIR method. In this region of ϵ , the position error also increases slowly. For $\epsilon > 0.32$ the opposite is true: there is not so much to gain in runtime, whereas the error increases more rapidly. So a choice of $\epsilon \approx 0.3$ could be reasonable in order to balance accuracy and speed. In other situation, other considerations might apply; for instance, for the special case of uniform flow, any ϵ might be used.

5.2. The SPE 10 case. This test case is taken from the tenth SPE comparative solution project, Model 2, see <http://www.spe.org/csp/datasets/set02.htm>. The original fine scale model is a Cartesian grid of $60 \times 220 \times 85$ grid cells.

Test 1: Layer 14. To set up a 2D simulation, we pull out layer number 14 and ignore the z -coordinates. Each interior grid point of the resulting grid is perturbed slightly (20%) to get an irregular grid. The original permeability is left unchanged in each perturbed cell. No-flow boundary conditions are applied, with an injector in the lower left corner and a producer in the upper right corner, see Figure 6. Streamlines are then initiated at the injector cell and traced to the producer. We consider four streamline starting points

FIGURE 6. SPE 10 case. CVIP with $\epsilon = 0.05$ (Left). CVIP with $\epsilon = 0.5$ (Right)

at the injector cell. For each starting point we trace the streamline with three different methods: CVIR, CVIP, and SFM. The only difference between the two plots in Figure 6, is the relative tolerance used with the CVIP method. For $\epsilon = 0.5$ in Figure 6 (right), we get large errors in the CVIP method compared to the CVIR method (and the SFM method). For $\epsilon = 0.05$ in Figure 6 (left), there is hardly any difference between the methods. In Table 1 the time-of-flight at the producer is shown for all the methods.

TABLE 1. Time-of-flight at the producer for the different methods

	SL1	SL2	SL3	SL4
SFM	1.8016e+06	2.1706e+06	1.6297e+06	1.3567e+06
CVIR	1.7990e+06	2.2308e+06	1.6556e+06	1.3584e+06
CVIP ($\epsilon = 0.05$)	1.7985e+06	2.2613e+06	1.6562e+06	1.3575e+06
CVIP ($\epsilon = 0.5$)	2.2433e+06	2.5604e+06	1.6655e+06	1.3842e+06

Test 2: All Layers. For each layer in the SPE case we consider the same setup as in the previous test. We increase the number of streamlines to ten, and trace from equally distributed starting points on the two injector faces. Let τ_R and τ_P be the time-of-flight at the producer for a particular streamline computed by CVIR and CVIP, respectively. Then the error for that streamline is measured as $|\tau_R - \tau_P|/\tau_R$. For each layer we take the average over all ten streamlines. The base-ten logarithm of the resulting error is shown in Figure 7 (left) for different values of ϵ . In Figure 7 (right) we have plotted the

FIGURE 7. SPE 10 case. Left: Error in CVIP for different layers and different ϵ . Right: Average error of CVIP over all layers for different ϵ .

average of the errors over all layers. A value of -2 corresponds to a 1% relative error in the time-of-flight. This is achieved on average for $\epsilon \approx 0.07$. The results show that the relative errors vary from 100% to 0.1% for different layers, streamlines, and tolerances ϵ . The right figure shows that the average error increases with ϵ , as expected. We believe that the high values for, e.g., $\epsilon = 0.05$ (red curve) in some layers (Figure 7 (left)) are not related to the tolerance, or the tracing method (CVIP). By following a particular streamline with a large error, we found that the error was a result of large variations in permeability, which for some grid cells caused the streamline to be extremely sensitive to the entry point.

5.3. Conclusion. We have tested the CVIP method on 2D irregular grids and compared it with the CVIR, SFM, and EFM methods. Experience with the 2D case can be valuable when extending the method to 3D. For uniform or almost uniform flow, CVIP is as efficient as the EFM method. Since the CVIP method is adaptive, it is possible to shift

to a more efficient and accurate method (e.g., the EFM, which is as accurate as CVIR in 2D) when the velocity field becomes less uniform. Similarly, in 3D one could make an adaptive method in which CVIP is the default choice and the more accurate CVIR is applied in regions where the velocity field changes rapidly. We have seen that if the tolerance of the CVIP method is chosen too high, meaning that we accept large errors in our approximation of the velocity, we are likely to get large errors in the streamlines. Accordingly, an error estimate for the CVIP method that can be used to control the tolerance, would be of great value.

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